

Research Article

Analysis and optimization of locally available lead ore by icp –oes

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Abstract: In this project, analysis of lead ore of Dalian region was carried out and then lead extracted from the ore. Lead is a grey colored metal, which is not found in free form, rather it is found in mineral with other metals such as Sulphur. Galena is the most commonly present lead ore. The technique used for the analysis of lead ore was ICP (Inductively Coupled Plasma). Lead ore was grinded to make powder with the help of pestle and mortar. This powder was taken as a sample and dissolved in concentrated HNO₃ and aqua Regia separately for the preparation of solutions. Aqua Regia is a mixture of HNO₃ and HCL with molar ratio 1:3 respectively. Ore was digested by heating in microwave oven in case of HNO₃ and at hot plate in case of aqua Regia. After digestion, solutions were filtered and diluted with distilled water. Nebulizer of ICP converts the solution to aerosol, which was analyzed and detected. It gives the composition of metals in the ore. Lead was present in large quantity in the ore, which was taken for analysis in this project. For extraction, lead was heated in a furnace with a limestone in the presence of coke, which acts as reducing agent and also used for the purpose of heat. Lead obtained from this method is 99% pure.

Keywords: Lead ore, inductively coupled plasma, aqua regia, analysis

1. Introduction

In the periodic table, lead has a place with the other metals in group 14. Group 14 also contains C; Sn. Lead has the maximum metallic qualities of this group. The nuclear number of this metal is 82 and a mass number is of 207. It has two oxidation states (+2 and +4) and four effective isotopes (204Pb, 206Pb, 207Pb and 208Pb). Out of these four isotopes, 208Pb is present in large quantity, about 52 % of the total mass [1]. The lead is present in a compact form in ores and minerals. These dark slate ores are important for the presence of lead in natural matter. Loess contains a normal Pb substance of 13 mg per kg. Lead is a stable element with silvery dark color.

It is universally present metal. In a buried state, lead can be distinguished from other metals, for example in air, sediment and in the most natural structure. Lead is the most important metal in the world and used widely. It sometimes comes in the essential form. Generally, it occurs as a mixtures, composites and complexes. Lead is used in electric accumulator batteries, radiation shields, channels and housings for the electrically coupled guide wire as lead insert. Lead makes composite with other metals and then used in pipe equipment [2]. Organic mixtures contain metallic lead for example tetraethyl lead and tetra methyl lead, which are more toxic than individual lead. These two natural lead components are used as part of anti-knocking agent in engine. Lead, additionally, combined with inorganic mixtures and also the salts of the frames. Lead is also present as lead nitrate, lead chromate and lead oxide. These mixtures have been used as part of a variety of materials, for example sprays, shades, colors, crystals, plastics and elastics [3]. In the earth, the lead found as a salt in the mineral metals. About 3000 years ago, the development of the essential lead has begun. In addition, the huge Spanish and Greek excavations included the characteristic rearrangement of lead. The Roman area was the fundamental organization for using many lead; without a doubt, the word plumbum, lead derived from Latin, which is also used for symbolic representation of lead as Pb. Lead is sweet in taste to some degree, so it contains a superior material to normal wine, which was then mixed throughout Europe Galena is also known as lead look. It is present as cubic ore structure that still has octahedral profiles. It is knowingly linked to dispersion minerals, calcite and fluorine for valuable purposes [4]. Deposits of minerals are the essential principle used by the researchers. Due to the weak point of solution, it was far from difficult to discharge without blurring. In some ores, the galenite contains about 1-2% of silver, a result that is taken transcendently. Galena minerals regularly contain noteworthy values of silver because minerals follow sulfonate silver or solid in the Galena [5]. The research was carried out to analyze the lead ore. Moreover it was aimed to characterize the ore whether a valuable metal such as Gold is present in ore. Previous Research showed that lead is used in industries. It was used in kajal for protection of eyes from sun light. It is also used as semiconductor. It is mostly used in batteries. Due to its extensive use it was being extracted from ores. But researchers have not focused other metals coupled with lead in lead ores. In this research characterization of lead ore was carried out to liberate other valuable metals from lead ores. Galena is the generally found lead mineral, lead sulphide in universal (PbS). By dissolution of hot lead oxide (PbO) and sulphur dioxide (SO₂), sulphide is

oxidized to a sulphite (PbSO_3). Sulphur dioxide (SO_2), (e.g. carbon dioxide for the state indicated above) is heated at high temperature and reduces the lead oxide. Other smaller ores are cerussite, anglesite, Pyromorphite, Mimetite and Wulfenite, which give different parts of time a significant amount of lead and galvanized silver [6]. Analysis of isotopes of lead is a comparatively new research of this growing group. Lead has also its own characteristics, merits and demerits like other members of group. These peculiarities and its merits and demerits are mentioned earlier. Through the analysis of isotopes of lead, minerals of lead can be detected geologically from which antique leads were found. If precise ores cannot be recognized, the substances can still be categorized according to their joint source [7]. Analysis of lead isotopes needs little amount of sample and the results do not depend on the ancient studies odd lead ores. The advantage of analysis of lead isotope is the blessed consequence of a threefold chance. According to history lead was one of those metals which were extracted first. Hence it is associated to many ancient objects, areas and times [8]. Galena is its major ore of lead and is easily extracted from this mineral. After its extraction, it was rapidly brought into use. It was used in amalgams, dyes, greasepaints, drugs, bifocals, coatings, and others. During the extraction of silver, it was largely formed as a side artefact. It was large in amount and comparatively low-cost. Geographically, lead differs in isotopic ratios in different ores, few metals do so. Gathering these three fold features, one has the foundation of a very valuable archaeometry implement. Lead element has four isotopes: ^{208}Pb , ^{207}Pb , ^{206}Pb , and ^{204}Pb . Out of these ^{208}Pb , ^{207}Pb and ^{206}Pb are decayed products of radioactivity of uranium and thorium [9]. There are significance differences in half lives of these elements, therefore, geologically, lead is found in different isotopes which are altering regularly. Further due to variation in the isotopes of lead in different geological regions, uranium and thorium are changing largely. However, mostly lead is isolated from parent uranium and thorium during mineral development [10]. Isotopic ratio of lead becomes fixed and do not alter in the ore. By measuring the different isotopic composition accurately, the different ores are analyzed which maybe different or same to the lead containing source. The detail characterizations of lead ore deposit from Baluchistan state of Pakistan carried out with ICP based techniques. Galena was taken as main ore. The results showed that lead was the main 95% of the metals was lead. Other elements like Zn, Al, Mg, Ti, Sn were in trace amounts.

2. Methodology

2.1 Lead collection

Galena is the chief source of lead. These ores are exposed along with the other minerals of sulfide, either of ore maybe present chiefly. Other elements may also present in lead minerals; as lead sulfide, carbonate and quartz. Lead sulfides are considered as metal ore when it is present in collection. The remaining ore is named as gangue [11]. The lead metal which is isolated from lead ore is a mild in nature. It is flexible metal and can be converted into other products. It has color of blue white. It is highly dense, and difficult to dissolve. It dissolved only in concentrated Nitric acid and aqua Regia during extraction of gold. Zinc or silver, it can be isolated as side product. In Pakistan, some deposits of lead metal are discovered in Lasbela-Khuzdar area of Baluchistan Province during inspection by Geological Survey of Pakistan. Some lead ore deposits are also present in Punjab Province; i.e. D.G. Khan a Taunsa Sharif has many resources of lead. Kohe-e-Sulaiman Mountains contains number of ores [12]. Figure 1 shows the map of ore deposits in Pakistan.

Figure 1 Map of Ore deposits in Pakistan

2.2 Sample Preparation

Two to three lead ores were taken. From each ore some fragments were taken. These fragments were washed to avoid any contamination. Then these fragments were grinded with the help of pestle and mortar made of iron. Pestle and mortar were also washed to avoid any dust particle which can contaminate lead ore. The process of grinding was done in clear environment and apparatus used was clean to avoid any contamination. After 30 minutes of grinding the ore fragments are converted into powder. This powder was taken in a clean filter paper. 50g of ore was weighed through weighing balance. This 30g powder of lead ore was taken as sample which is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Powdered lead ore

Two solutions were prepared the firstly In nitric acid of 0.15 g ore sample was taken and dissolved in 10mL of nitric acid. Ore was digested in microwave oven for 12 minutes at 265oC temperature. It was filter out with the help of what man filter paper. Then the solution was diluted to 100mL by addition of distilled water in a volumetric flask. Secondly in the Aqua Regia of 0.15g of ore sample was dissolved in 10mL of Aqua Regia. Ore was digested by heating this solution at hot plate. After digestion the solution was filtered out by using what man filter paper. Then it was diluted up to 100mL by adding distilled water in a volumetric flask. Another benefit of ICP discharges is that they are relatively free of contamination, because the electrodes are completely outside the reaction chamber. By contrast, in capacitive coupled plasma (CCP), the

electrodes are often placed inside the reactor and are thus exposed to the plasma and subsequent reactive chemical species.

Figure 3 Lead preparation

In both cases, residue was remained after filtration. Residue was dried and weighed. This residue can be used for the lead tests. Technique used for this purpose is ICP (inductively coupled Plasma). An inductively coupled plasma (ICP) or transformer coupled plasma (TCP) is a type of plasma source in which the energy is supplied by electric currents which are produced by electromagnetic induction, that is, by time-varying magnetic fields. Mostly ICP-MS solid materials are analyzed by using technique named as inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy. This technique was industrialized in 1980s. It can be used for the detection of different solid materials, glass, metal elements such as lead, iron, chromium, gold, silver etc. and for the analysis of other expensive stones. ICP-MS is an advance technique with many characteristics; i.e. it can be used for the depth analysis, detection at spot, preparation of sample, with low time detection, and it can analyze metals found in traces. References materials are used to avoid the elemental fractionation [13]. These references contain composition similar to the metal analyzed. It consists of many parts: Nebulizer: It converts the solution into aerosol for analysis Source: ICP source is consisting of three electrodes which is known as tripod. Excitation area is situated in the middle of this tripod. Analyzer: It is used to analyze the aerosol introduced by Nebulizer Detector: It detects the results. The structure of ICP is shown in Figure 4. Plasma electron temperatures can range between $\sim 60,000$ K and $\sim 1000,000$ K (~ 6 eV - ~ 100 eV), [5] and are usually several orders of magnitude greater than the temperature of the neutral species. Argon ICP plasma discharge temperatures are typically $\sim 5,500$ to $6,500$ K [8] and are therefore

comparable to that reached at the surface (photosphere) of the sun (~4,500 K to ~6,000 K). ICP discharges are of relatively high electron density, on the order of 10^{15} cm^{-3} . As a result, ICP discharges have wide applications where high-density plasma (HDP) is needed.

Figure 4 Structure of ICP

First of all, lead ore was analyzed for the detection of lead and other metals. Then by extraction process, lead was extracted. Two solutions were prepared as mentioned above. Each solution was kept in 100mL flask. One was prepared in nitric acid and other was prepared in aqua Regia. These solutions were analyzed by ICP. Nebulizer was placed in flask. It converts sample into aerosol and it is feed to excitation area in plasma. The sample is analyzed by analyzer and results are detected through detectors. These results show presence of different metals in ore. Galena is main ore of lead. It is also called lead sulphide as sulphur is present in it. Through flotation process sulphur was removed and remaining portion is known as gangue, which contains approximately 80 percent lead ore [14]. Impurities are still present like zinc, sulphur, antimony etc. Galena ore is reacted with O_2 to remove sulphur completely.

limestone. Coke is used as reducing agent and also for the purpose of heat [15]. The mixture is heated at furnace and molten lead is collected, which is 99% pure.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis

By analysis of locally available lead ore, it is testified that it contains lead in large quantity [16] other metals are also present in this sample. Some metals were in traces and cannot be calculated. For Aqua Regia solution the Analysis of ore dissolving through Aqua Regia has given results which are mentioned in the Table 1.

Table 1 Amounts of excess metals in the Aqua Regia and nitric Acid solutions

Sr #	Elements	In Aqua Regia	In HNO ₃
1	Pb	33.4349	52.1140
2	Zn	6.7580	7.40599
3	Total	39.5929	59.51999

Significant amounts of metals that are effectively present in substantial amounts of ICP. Similarly, these values have also been discovered by ICP. The Table 2&3 shows the values of detection by ICP and traces respectively.

Table 2 Metals values detected by ICP

Sr#	Elements	In Aqua Regia	In HNO ₃
1	Cu	0.103647	0.12599
2	Al	0.0341244	0.0583921
3	Cd	0.0101	0.01131
4	Total	0.147814	0.1956921

Table 3 Metals values observed by traces

Sr#	Elements	In Aqua Regia	In HNO ₃
1	Cr	0.004	0.001
2	Hg	0.002	0.005
3	Ni	0.003	0.008
4	Se	0.001	0.004

5	Sr	0.002	0.003
6	As	0.002	0.003
7	B	0.002	0.003
8	Total	0.016	0.027

The uncalculated metals are the Barium (Ba), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Mo, Sb, Sn. The Extraction of lead is defined as that Lead is extracted from the lead ore by mixing it with coke and limestone, a mixture was formed. This mixture was placed in furnace and heated. Molten lead was isolated. This lead is 95% pure [17]. Tests for Lead For the presence of lead of some tests were also performed such as the Reaction with Dilute HCL of 10mL solution of lead ore in Nitric acid was taken. Dilute HCL was added to this solution. White precipitates are appeared which confirm the presence of lead [18]. Another test of Reaction with Potassium chromate of 10mL solution of sample was taken. Solution of potassium chromate K_2CrO_4 . Yellow precipitates is formed due to formation of $PbCrO_4$. This confirms the presence of lead [19]. Finally the Reaction with KI of 10mL solution was taken in a beaker for 5mL of KI solution was added to this solution. Formation of yellow precipitates shows the presence of lead [20].

4. Conclusion

It is concluded that extraction of metals from ores is important. Mineral chemistry is most important in this regard. By these techniques an ore can be analyzed which shows presence of different metals in the mineral. These metals can be extracted and used for many good purposes. This is an easy work and 70 to 80% work can be obtained. Inductively Coupled plasma is an important tool for the analysis of ore. Extraction process can be done by heating ore in an electric furnace. Approximately 95% pure lead is isolated by this process.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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